

Molecular Study of Breast Cancer Gene Polymorphism Effects on Udder Diseases in Cows

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Abstract

The study was conducted at the Private Station on samples consisting of 60 blood samples taken from 100 Friesian cows in 3rd and 4th parity during the year 2022 to determine the effect of single nucleotide polymorphism of BRCA gene mastitis infection rate. Results indicated that the rate of mastitis infection for all cows samples differed significantly in cows with wild genotype (AA) it's about 51.4% while the rates in both hetero or mutant were 40.2 and 8.4% respectively. Mastitis rate differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among cows groups in 3rd parity according to its genotype, the infection rate was 33.5, 42 and 24.5% for cows with wild, hetero and mutant genotype respectively. Results showed that the mastitis rate differed significantly ($P < 0.01$) among cows groups in 4th parity according to its genotype, the infection rate was 41, 43.1 and 15.9% for cows with wild, hetero and mutant genotype respectively.

Keywords: *Friesian cows, mastitis BRCA gene polymorphism.*

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Introduction

Cows are among the most important large domestic animals and are widely distributed around the world due to the significance of their products in meeting human nutritional needs, particularly milk production, which accounts for 82.5% of the total milk produced by other dairy cattle species (Hernández-Castellano et al., 2019). Holstein breed is described as the most widespread and the best milk producing breed. It is a European breed found in most countries since it adapts easily in different environmental conditions especially along the coasts of Netherlands and Denmark. It is also characterized by the fact that it has good reproductive performance and the ability to produce large milk quantities among other productive qualities (Arif et al., 2009; Duvenhage, 2017). According to Miglior and his peers (2017), the developments of the sphere of molecular biology and its utilization as the means of breeding and improvement program creation of animals are associated with the promotion of productive characteristics. Markers are also important in determining the variance, which categorizes individuals to be selected according to morphological and productive characteristics, with respect to the kind and presence of these markers on the DNA (Teneva and Petrovic, 2010). The variance between the individual of individuals as measured by the difference in the markers and the variance in the genetic compositions is due to the difference in the insertion, deletion, duplication and mutations. Based on these variations, individuals are selected (Deb et.al., 2012). In numerous studies on animals, Hansen (2004) relied on

molecular genetic markers for selecting heat tolerance traits in Zebu cattle and other European breeds. Ashwell et.al., (2004) demonstrated that there are quantitative trait loci (QTL) that affect fertility in females and milk production traits in Holstein cows; individual selection can be made based on these loci and their genetic composition. Yang et.al., (2010) used markers to select cattle based on variance in reproductive and fertility traits. The major aim of this study is to determine the effect of genetic mutation in BRCA1 gene (3rd exon) on the mastitis rate in Friesian cows reared in Iraq and use the BRCA1 polymorphism as a genetic marker to improve the cows performance.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Animals

The study was conducted at the Private Station on samples consisting of 100 blood samples taken from 100 Friesian cows during their 3rd and 4th lactation seasons. The system used for cows breeding at the station is in open and semi-open pens, with closed facilities for young calves. The herd is managed according to a program that includes feeding, preparation for the breeding season, and arrangements for the stages of pregnancy and calving, as well as health and veterinary care.

Somatic Cell Determining

The animals used in this study were Friesian dairy cows, black and white spotted, in their third production season. Blood samples (100 blood samples) were drawn using a 10-milliliter medical syringe and placed in vacuum tubes (EDTA). Additionally, 300 milk samples (3 samples per cow) were collected using collection tubes and transported directly to the laboratory after cooling, according to the Ericsson method (2009). Some measurements were taken directly by observing behavioral changes in the animals at the highest temperature extremes as well as at the lowest temperature extremes.

DNA Isolate

A total of 100 blood samples were taken from the udder vein of cows during their third calving season using a complete blood collection kit, with one sample per cow and a volume of 8 milliliters, using 10-milliliter medical syringes after cleaning and sterilizing the udder vein area with 70% ethanol. The samples were transported in a refrigerated container to the laboratory for preservation by freezing at -4°C and immediate DNA extraction.

The primers were selected for the purpose of conducting molecular detection and identifying the phenotypic diversity of the BRCA1 gene.

Primer Determination

A special primer was designed to amplify the target site of BRCA1 gene: CATTGTTGAGCACACAGTAAGT and CAC TCT GCG CTG CTAGAT forward and reverse respectively with annealing temperature about 60 c° and the product size was 760 bp.

After the polymerization reaction was completed, the presence or absence of mutations was detected using sequencing by sending the samples to be read in South Korea and receiving the results via email.

The statistical program SAS (2016) was used to analyze the obtained data according to the chi- squire test to compare between observed and expected rates of mastitis infection.

Results and Discussion

Results in Fig.1 indicated that the rate of mastitis infection for all cows samples differed significantly in cows with wild genotype (AA) it's about 51.4% while the rates in both hetero or mutant were 40.2 and 8.4% respectively.

Figure 1. Relationship of Mastitis Rate with BRCA Gene Polymorphism

Results showed that the mastitis rate differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among cows groups in 3rd parity according to its genotype (Fig. 2), the infection rate was 33.5, 42 and 24.5% for cows with wild, hetero and mutant genotype respectively.

Figure 2. Relationship of Mastitis Rate with BRCA Gene Polymorphism in Cows with 3rd Parity

Results showed that the mastitis rate differed significantly ($P < 0.01$) among cows groups in 4th parity according to its genotype (Fig. 3), the infection rate was 41, 43.1 and 15.9% for cows with wild, hetero and mutant genotype respectively.

Figure 3. Relationship of Mastitis Rate with BCRA Gene Polymorphism in Cows with 4th Parity

Many studies indicate that cows' sensitivity to udder diseases increases with their milk production. Conversely, a certain degree of genetic success can be achieved in this trait. This raises the question about the available possibilities to achieve a desirable genetic development in both milk production and mastitis resistance simultaneously (Pegolo et.al, 2022). Generally, relationships, and specifically genetic ones, indicate the biological potentials available for achieving such a combination. Relationships between traits are usually expressed in terms of correlation coefficients, which describe the type and strength of the relationship between different traits. Additionally, inappropriate relationships between traits form what is known as trait antagonism, which makes it impossible to develop the traits simultaneously (Cheng et.al., 2020).

Increasing the milk productivity of cows and improving their resistance to mastitis necessitates our attention to the environmental factors that contribute to the occurrence of mastitis in order to eliminate them (Payorala et.al., 2003).

We should focus our genetic improvement programs for bulls and cows on traits that enhance the resistance of cows to mastitis, such as considering the resistance trait of the bull's daughters to this disease in bull selection programs. Additionally, we should emphasize the content of solids in the milk as part of the selection traits (Barreiro et.al., 2018).

Genetics plays a very important role in milk production, and all dairy cattle breeders select livestock breeds based on this principle. However, it is essential to understand that genetic traits have no value unless the appropriate environment is provided (Shkromada et.al., 2019).

For instance, if there is a cow with good genetic traits, it can produce its maximum potential when the environmental factors and conditions are suitable for it. On the other hand, the contrary can take place when the environment is unfavorable, despite the same genes endowed, meaning that genetic factors will become useless unless the right conditions will be offered (Rolling et.al., 2015; Liang et.al., 2017). The size and age of the animal may have an effect on the production of milk. As an example, the fourth season is the most favorable to milk production, and the first and second season are associated with the least (Rowe et.al., 2020).

This is because of the augmented dimension of the udder and the size of the rumen which is capable of holding higher levels of energy meal to make milk. According to the research findings, the choice of animal used to produce milk based on genetic and phenotypic characteristics and then providing it with the right environment is one of the most significant issues, which is the subclinical mastitis (Godden et.al., 2003).

Conclusion

In this study concluded that this is important factor as it affects the powers of milk production in quantity and quality. The proven scientific fact of research is that on every incidence of clinical mastitis, 20 or 40 cases of subclinical mastitis exist that is, cases that are not apparent.

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